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rustamkhurramov@mail.ru**THE NOTIONS OF “KNOWLEDGE”, “ACTION” AND “LEARNING”****Abstract**

Researchers have argued that teachers' knowledge can be evidenced by the ways they elicit and respond to student ideas. We analyze data from a four-year study of nine high school teachers who designed formative assessment tasks and learned about student thinking with a learning progression for natural selection. We coded teacher questions, student responses, and teacher feedback in classroom videos collected across four years. Through sequential analysis, we found that teachers came to ask more questions that elicited student ideas, and also became more likely to respond to student ideas with pushing feedback at the end of the study.

Key words: knowledge, action, learning, concept, cultural value, strong

Annotatsiya

Tadqiqotchilarning ta'kidlashicha, o'qituvchilarning bilimlari o'quvchilarning g'oyalarini o'zlashtirish va ularga javob berish usullari bilan tasdiqlanishi mumkin. Biz to'qqizta o'rta maktab o'qituvchilari ishtirokidagi to'rt yillik tadqiqot ma'lumotlarini tahlil qilamiz, ular formativ baholash vazifalarini ishlab chiqdilar va tabiiy tanlanish uchun o'rganish jarayoni bilan o'quvchilarning fikrlashini o'rgandilar. Biz to'rt yil davomida yig'ilgan sinf videolarida o'qituvchi savollari, talaba javoblari va o'qituvchining fikr-mulohazalarini kodladik. Ketma-ket tahlil qilish orqali biz o'qituvchilar talabalarning g'oyalarini uyg'otadigan ko'proq savollar berishga kelganini va tadqiqot oxirida fikr-mulohazalarni bildirish orqali talabalar g'oyalariga javob berish ehtimoli ko'proq ekanligini aniqladik.

Kalit so'zlar: bilim, harakat, o'rganish, tushuncha, madaniy qadriyat, kuchli

Аннотация

Исследователи утверждают, что о знаниях учителей можно судить по тому, как они выявляют идеи учеников и реагируют на них. Мы анализируем данные четырехлетнего исследования девяти учителей старших классов, которые разработали задания для формативной оценки и узнали о мышлении учащихся с помощью прогрессии обучения для естественного отбора. Мы закодировали вопросы учителей, ответы учеников и отзывы учителей в классных видео, собранных за четыре года. Посредством последовательного анализа мы обнаружили, что учителя стали задавать больше вопросов, которые выявляли идеи учащихся, а также стали более склонны реагировать на идеи учащихся с помощью подталкивающей обратной связи в конце исследования.

Ключевые слова: знание, действие, обучение, концепт, культурная ценность, сильная сторона.

At the present time the concept is the key notion of cognitive linguistics.

Y.S. Stepanov defines the concept as follows: “The concept – is like a bunch of culture in human consciousness in the form of what culture is a mental world of man. And, on the other hand, the concept – is that by which a person – ordinary person, not “the creator of cultural values” – himself enters in the culture, and in some cases affects it[12].

S.A. Askoldov, who one of the first referred to the study of concepts, considered the concept “mental entity that replaces in the mental activity a lot of objects of the same kind.” He further said that “one should not, of course, think that the concept is always a replacement of real objects, it may be the replacement of different kinds[21].”

G.G. Slyshkin and V. I. Karasik understand the concept as “a multidimensional mental unit with a dominant value element.” Concept groups around some “strong” point of consciousness, from which associative vectors diverge. The most relevant associations for native speakers are the nuclear of concept, the less significant – the periphery[13].

According to their view the concept hasn't clear boundaries. Language or speech units, which updated the central point of the concept, is the name of the concept[22]. Concept characterized by a set of “entrances”, i.e. units of speech and language with which

this concept is actualized in the mind of its informant. Entrances to the concept may relate to different levels of language. To appeal to one and the same concept lexemes, idioms, free combinations, suggestions, and texts are used[5].

Z.D. Popova and I.A. Sternin define the concept as a complex mental entity which is in the process of mental activity turns the different sides actualizing in the process of thinking its different signs and layers; appropriate signs or layers of the concept may not have the linguistic symbols in native language[23]. Concept are represented in language with ready lexemes from the lexical-phraseological language system, free phrases, structural and positional diagrams bringing model propositions (syntactic concepts), the text and the set of texts[40].

Concepts can be stable – have ascribed to them linguistic means of verbalization, and unstable – don't have assigned to them verbalization, yet emerging, deeply personal, rarely, or almost not verbalized[38]. The presence of a linguistic expression for the concept, its regular verbalization support the concept stability, steady state, make it well known (because the meanings of words, which is transmitted, are well known, they are interpreted by native speakers, recognized in the dictionaries)[24].

The authors propose the following model of the concept: a sensual base image is the nuclear of the concept, acting as a universal way of encoding the object code[39]. This image belongs to the everyday layer of consciousness and according to some observations, has an operational or substantive nature, based on biodynamic and sensuous fabric of consciousness[6]. Base image is surrounded with a concrete sense by its origin the cognitive layer, which reflects the sensual perceived properties, attributes of the object[41].

This layer together with the base layer refers to the everyday layer of consciousness. Further in the structure of the concept (although not all concepts) are allocated more abstract layers, reflecting a certain stage of everyday signs related to the reflective layer of consciousness[14].

Finally, the interpretative field of concept, which includes the evaluation of the content, interpreting some cognitive signs and forming the national consciousness arising from the contents of the concept the advice about comprehension of reality, may be

associated with the spiritual level of consciousness, which involves a broad sense, an assessment of the concept in terms of its value to the nation[25].

The different terms and differentiations that knowledge management literature has provided in the conceptualization of knowledge have been presented. Knowledge is in people's heads, it differs from information or data, it is individual, and in some instances it can be made public or shared as information[26].

In addition, the difference between various types of knowledge has been explained in terms of content. Andriessen (2006, p. 97) identifies six different metaphors in his analysis of the treatment of knowledge in key publications of the knowledge management field: knowledge as something physical, as a wave, as a living organism, as thought and feelings, as a process and as a structure[7].

In the present work, knowledge is understood both as the structure and the content of the mental schemas[42]. Therefore, this study could be said to use knowledge as "something physical" and "as a structure" as defined by Andriessen. It also includes the idea of knowledge as feelings since the schemas have important emotional components[15].

Further, it includes knowledge as a process, as a wave and as a living organism, since these three elements refer to the idea that knowledge is in a constant dialectic process with the reality it represents[27]. The frame and the content are reinforced or change in each action that we perform. It is through action that we test our schema in the real world. This action will inform us about the schema that in turn will or will not change. In this way, action develops our knowledge, and knowledge is therefore a dynamic entity[28].

Knowledge as a static entity never changes. The positivistic view of science maintains that scientific inquiry looks for objective and universal knowledge, what traditionally has been called Truth with a capital T. However, post-positivistic views criticize the idea of a universal truth and propose the existence of different truths. Thus there will not be a unique, invariant knowledge but different types of knowledge viewed from different perspectives[16].

In the management literature, as Demarest (1997, p. 375) has pointed out, interest is focused on commercial knowledge, as in the following: The goal of commercial knowledge

is not truth, but effective performance: not 'what is right' but 'what works' or even 'what works better' where better is defined in competitive and financial contexts[8].

In a similar vein, Spender (2002, p. 151) has indicated that: We need to keep a careful eye on the utility of theorizing [about knowledge], whether our conclusions can ever be reattached to our discipline's established empirical work in economics, strategy, competition, institutionalized theorizing, management and so forth[29].

The dynamic feature of knowledge is thus related to the idea that knowledge must be translated into and associated with action (Blacker, 1995; Hunt, 2003; Elkjaer, 2003)[37-76]. Further, the action uses knowledge but does not "consume" the knowledge that can be re-used in its modified form[30]. Thus it is important to mention that "knowledge is not 'consumed' in a process, it sometimes increases through use" (Wiig et al. 1997, p. 16, emphasis added; Halal, 1998, p. 13). Through this process of adaptation, or equilibrium in Piaget's terms, knowledge, action and learning are closely linked together[17].

To conclude, it is important to note that knowledge is related to learning. The act of learning provides knowledge and understanding, which in turn feed further learning". As has been already argued, learning can be regarded as the adaptation of mental structures to the specific realities that an individual confronts[31].

Knowledge, understood both as content and as schema, will therefore be constructed during this process of adaptation through its interaction with the environment[32]. When we are presented with data (facts, impressions), we will examine that specific information (which has some meaning and structure for us) with the knowledge that we already have[18].

In fact, the previous knowledge will guide the type of data that we seek, or beyond that, the information we seek and are capable of understanding. If that specific information content (either know-what, why, how or who) appears in adequate conditions of motivation, interest and attention, the content will be "absorbed" into the mental model (or theory) that we are applying to that specific context[33]. The new content might not produce much change in the structure of the mental model (alpha answer), it might produce partial modification (beta answer) or it might result in a critical modification (gamma answer, significant learning or conceptual change)[9].

These changes in our schema constitute, in fact, learning. Learning is the process of transforming data into knowledge, making something public (information) into something private (knowledge).

The process of transforming knowledge into data is the process of teaching, understood broadly[34]. The information that starts the process of learning is usually the articulation of someone's knowledge that served to codify and externalize her/his knowledge. If the students (or any listener or reader) incorporate the data that has been externalized, then there is learning.

Finally, it is important to mention that knowledge might be acquired through different means[43].

Knowledge is not only created through theoretical means (such as reading or analyzing information); learning also occurs by doing. Thus when we act, our acts "teach" us, providing us with information on our performance[35]. This process of learning is not necessarily a conscious one, and can occur implicitly without the individual realizing it; in this way we acquire tacit knowledge.

To sum up, this paper on the conceptualization of knowledge considers learning and knowledge to be totally interrelated, since learning is the process of creating knowledge and knowledge guides the process of learning[36]. Learning occurs constantly and throughout the entire life span, this is it is a lifelong, life-wide process[19].

It is clear that knowledge and learning are complex concepts that are difficult to define. The above discussion tries to clarify them and present some relationships between knowledge and other related constructs, but it cannot be seen as a comprehensive review of the conceptualization of knowledge[10].

Tacit knowledge is crucial for Small and Medium Enterprises that rely heavily on the knowledge of their employees and that do not usually have very formalized systems for knowledge management.[20] On the other hand, bigger companies might have more formalized knowledge management systems, and might not need to rely as much on the tacit knowledge of their employees, but on information.

Thus, in terms of the promotion of innovation, understanding the nature of knowledge and its differences with other related terms is crucial in order to make right decisions in a highly competitive knowledge economy[11]. This also calls for understanding the process of learning and as a consequence the process of teaching. If learning is meant to occur as a lifelong, life-wide process, teaching and learning are necessarily interconnected outside formal institutions. Pedagogical principals might be of interest for the business community in order to make their workforce more adaptable and able to learn.

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